

FROM DIGITAL ARCHIVES TO THE SEMANTIC WEB

REDMIX Online Seminar Series

3 - 17
December
2025

3 December • 5:00-7:00 pm

Reshaping and Aggrandising Archives from Analogue and Digital to Semantic Web: a Long Journey to “Mandeland”?

Mpho Ngoepe (University of South Africa)

10 December • 5:00-7:00 pm

**Data Modeling as the Foundation of Digital Humanities:
From Historical Sources to Semantic Structures**

Dinara Gagarina (Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg & Herder Institute for Historical Research on East Central Europe – Institute of the Leibniz Association, Marburg)

17 December • 5:00-7:00 pm

Linked Data Fundamentals: Standards, Ontologies, and Tools

Riccardo Albertoni (CNR-IMATI, Genoa)

Organized & moderated by **Tiziana Pasciuto** (University of Turin)

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